

Impacts of organizational support perception, Workload and Organizational Culture On Organizational Citizenship Behavior through job satisfaction in frontliner employees of Bank Mandiri Jember, Indonesia

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Abstract: Human Resources are the main key factor in achieving company goals. The form and objectives of the company, various visions are designed for the benefit of the company where in implementing its mission it is managed and managed by good human resources. This means that humans are a strategic resource in all company activities. OCB behavior possessed by employees in the human resources management section needs to always be improved so that company goals can be achieved. The success and development of a company cannot be separated from employees who are willing to play a role voluntarily in carrying out their duties and do not expect certain rewards. This research method uses quantitative with smartPLS. The sample used was 97 people. The results of this research indicate that there is a positive and insignificant influence between perceptions of organizational support on OCB. There are positive and insignificant results between perceived organizational support and job satisfaction. There are positive and significant results between workload and OCB. There are positive results and workload and job satisfaction. There are positive and significant results between organizational culture and OCB. There are positive and significant results between organizational culture and job satisfaction. There are positive and significant results between job satisfaction and OCB. There are results where there is an indirect influence between perceptions of organizational support, workload and organizational culture on OCB through job satisfaction as mediation.

Keywords: perception of organizational support, workload, organizational culture, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Human Resources are the main key factor in achieving company goals. The form and objectives of the company, various visions are designed for the benefit of the company where in implementing its mission it is managed and managed by good human resources. This means that humans are a strategic resource in all company activities. OCB behavior possessed by employees in the human resources management department needs to always be improved so that company goals can be achieved. The success and development of a company cannot be separated from employees who are willing to play a role voluntarily in carrying out their duties and do not expect certain rewards.

The digitalization carried out by PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) reduced employees, especially frontliners. Because everything was digital, in the end, initially there were various kinds of sales employees such as sales A, product B sales, and product C sales, and were streamlined to become general banking sales. The reduction in sales employees resulted in frontiers having to sell products, whereas previously frontiers were only tasked with serving customers. The general banking sales task has a target of selling products outside, while frontliners have a target of selling various products inside or when providing services to customers. Front-line employees responsible for sales in the office are vulnerable to experiencing problems at work such as excessive workload, stagnant sales, providing maximum service, and so on. The problems experienced by these employees show that the OCB of Bank Mandiri frontier employees needs to be improved. Employees with high levels of OCB will voluntarily work beyond the required tasks, including increasing workloads. Employees who have high OCB will tend to tolerate existing working conditions, including service and sales problems which are the new responsibilities of front-line employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Perception of Organizational Support

According to Atmaja (2019), perceived organizational support is a science that determines the extent to which an organization supports employees in various matters regarding work, appreciates employee contributions and provides concern for employee welfare, which has an impact on improving employee performance so that organizational goals are achieved well. According to Robert (1986), the variable perception of organizational support can be found through three indicators, namely:

- a. Justice, which is procedural justice which is used as a way to determine the equitable distribution of employee resources. Employees receive open information regarding work at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- b. Support from superiors, which is the employee's general view of the role of superiors, which involves superiors who value contributions and care about employee welfare. Employees are involved in decision making by leadership at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- c. Awards from the Organization and Working Conditions, which are all kinds of awards from the company given to employees, including: salary, promotions, employee development programs, job security, autonomy, work stress and organizational size. Employees receive awards for their achievements and employees receive adequate facilities to support their work at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area.

Workload

According to Menpan (2020) Workload is a number of activities that must be completed by an organization or the holder of a position within a certain time. According to Koesomo (2017), there are several indicators used to find out how much workload employees must complete, namely as follows:

- a. Job conditions, namely how far an employee understands his job well. Employees are able to understand working conditions at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- b. Use of working time, namely the use of appropriate time in accordance with the SOP that has been determined will certainly minimize employee workload. Employees carry out duties according to the time set by Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- c. Targets that must be achieved, namely, indirectly the work targets set by employees will influence the workload received by employees. Employees are able to complete work according to the targets set by Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

Organizational culture

According to Ading (2021), organizational culture is generally a philosophical statement, it can function as a binding demand for employees because it can be formally formulated in various company regulations and provisions. According to Hari (2019:14), the characteristics that influence organizational culture include:

- a. Innovative, namely taking into account the risk that each employee will pay sensitive attention to all problems that might pose a risk of loss to the organization as a whole. Employees have a desire to innovate
- b. Paying attention to each problem in detail, namely describing the thoroughness and thoroughness of employees in carrying out their duties. Employees do their work thoroughly
- c. Oriented to the results to be achieved, namely a manager's supervision of his subordinates is one way for managers to direct and empower them. Employees work oriented towards results as determined by Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- d. Oriented to all employee interests, namely the success or performance of the organization, one of which is determined by work teams, where teamwork can be formed if managers can supervise their subordinates well. Employees are able to work together with a team in carrying out work at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- e. Aggressive at work, that is, high productivity can be produced if employee performance can meet the standards required to carry out their duties. Employees have appropriate skills with the field of work at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area
- f. Maintaining and maintaining work stability, namely employees must be able to maintain their health condition so that it remains in top condition. Conditions like this can only be met if they regularly consume nutritious food based on the advice of a nutritionist. Employees are able to maintain their health condition so they can work well.

Job satisfaction

According to Robbins (2020) job satisfaction is about positive feelings about work as a result of evaluations carried out by individuals (position holders) regarding the characteristics of the job itself. According to Wibowo (2011), there are five indicators that influence the level of job satisfaction of an employee, including:

- a. Wages are the nominal wages a person receives as compensation for work completed in accordance with their needs and sense of justice. Employees are paid according to the work they do.
- b. Promotion, namely the possibility that someone can develop through promotion. A person can feel that there is a big possibility of being promoted or not, the promotion process is not open or open enough. This can also affect a person's level of job satisfaction. There is an opportunity for employees to get promotions at a higher level at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area.
- c. Supervision is defined as direction and control at the level of employees who are subordinate to them in an organization or group. Leaders become good mentors for employee career development at PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area.
- d. Profits, namely something that employees get from the company, for example; insurance, holidays, and other forms of facilities provided by the company. Many awards were received for employees who achieved targets at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area.
- e. Appreciation, namely assessing something by giving respect, being recognized and given an award. When employees do good work, leaders provide recognition that meets expectations.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

According to Wibowo (2019) explains that in the psychological concept, OCB is a psychological attribute that is continuum in nature. This means that OCB moves from the lowest to the highest spectrum. According to Robbins (2006) OCB indicators are as follows:

- a. Altruism, namely the behavior of employees in helping colleagues who are experiencing difficulties in the situation they are facing, both regarding tasks in the organization and other people's personal problems. Employees at Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area are happy to help colleagues who are having difficulty.
- b. Prudence (Conscientiousness), namely behavior shown by trying to exceed what the company expects. Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area employees complete their tasks as well as possible.
- c. Sportsmanship, namely behavior that tolerates less than ideal conditions in the organization without raising objections. Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area employees try to always follow the regulations or policies implemented by PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area.
- d. Politeness (Courtesy), namely maintaining good relationships with co-workers to avoid interpersonal problems. Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area employees are able to maintain good relationships with co-workers.
- e. Civic Morals (Civic Virtue), namely behavior that indicates responsibility for organizational life (following changes in the organization, taking the initiative to recommend how the organization's operations or procedures can be improved, and protecting the resources owned by the company). Employees are responsible for the tasks assigned by Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK RESEARCH

Gambar 2.1 Kerangka Konseptual (Sumber: Data Diolah)

INFORMATION:

- : Direct Influence
- - - - -: Indirect Influence

HYPOTHESIS

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Luxurious et al (2023), organizational support can increase self-confidence in teachers, thereby generating confidence in being an effective and efficient resource in the progress of the organization. According to Detnakarin & Rurkkhum (2019; 197) perceived organizational support proves that organizational support is an important variable in explaining reciprocity between employees and the organization where they work. Therefore, according to Haryokusumo (2015), it is hoped that organizations can provide support to their employees, because the perception of organizational support not only provides benefits for employees but can also improve organizational performance.

H1: Perception of organizational support has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The Influence of Workload on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Ferdy (2022) Organizational Citizenship Behavior is a way of behaving that goes beyond the expected work, which is not directly or explicitly felt by the appropriate reward framework is a preferred way of behaving that is not important for an employee's workload, but upholds strong work from the association. According to Komaruddin (1996:235), workload analysis is the process of determining the number of working hours people use or need to complete a job within a certain time, or in other words workload analysis aims to determine how many personnel and how many responsibilities or the appropriate workload is delegated to an officer.

H2: Workload has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Noer (2020) organizational culture can be used as a reference for employees in assessing the extent of achievement of performance goals. So it can be said that if the organizational culture is good, the quality of employee resources is good, which means that if the culture in the organization is of good quality, the quality of employees also tends to be good. The more employees follow existing norms and rules, the greater the OCB behavior they demonstrate can provide benefits to the organization.

H3: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction in Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Robbins (2020) job satisfaction is about positive feelings about work as a result of evaluations carried out by individuals (position holders) regarding the characteristics of the job itself. The strong perception of organizational support can cause employees to feel satisfaction in carrying out their work.

H4: Perception of organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

The Influence of Workload on Job Satisfaction in Frontliners at PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Ganis et al (2023) workload is the quantity and complexity of tasks that a person must complete within a certain period of time. Workload includes not only the amount of work to be done, but also the level of responsibility, time constraints, and available resources. The greater a person's workload, the greater the burden on his physical and mental capacity. According to Menpan (2020) Workload is a number of activities that must be completed by an organization or the holder of a position within a certain time.

H5: Workload has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction in Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Ganis et al (2023) Organizational culture is the conditions or habits that are usually carried out by employees or work in a company. Organizational culture can be positive towards the company and employee job satisfaction, and there can be negative traits towards the company and employee job satisfaction. Culture, as a common understanding of an organization's values, conventions, and behaviors, provides a strong foundation for workers' work experiences. A supportive, inclusive, and collaborative culture tends to increase job satisfaction. According to Ading (2021), organizational culture is generally a philosophical statement, it can function as a binding demand for employees because it can be formally formulated in various company rules and regulations.

H6: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area Frontliners Through Job Satisfaction

According to Detnakin & Rurkkhum (2019; 197) perceived organizational support proves that organizational support is an important variable in explaining reciprocity between employees and the organization where they work. Therefore, according to Haryokusumo (2015), it is hoped that organizations can provide support to their employees, because the perception of organizational support not only provides benefits for employees but can also improve organizational performance.

H7: Perception of organizational support has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through job satisfaction

The Influence of Workload on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area Frontliners Through Job Satisfaction

According to Menpan (2020) Workload is a number of activities that must be completed by an organization or the holder of a position within a certain time. Luthfan et al (2023) "The Influence of Workload and Work Environment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Through Employee Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Study at the Manpower, Transmigration and Energy Department of North Jakarta Administrative City)" in their research stated that workload has an effect positively and significantly towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through job satisfaction. Based on the theory and empirical evidence that has been mentioned, this research proposes the following hypothesis.

H8: Workload has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through job satisfaction

The influence of organizational culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area frontliners through job satisfaction

According to Kreitner & Kinichi (2014:62) defines organizational culture as a set of assumptions that are shared and implicitly accepted for granted and held by a group that determines how it is felt, thought about, and reacted to various environments.

H9: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through job satisfaction

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the Frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember Area

According to Mohammad et al (2021) The Influence of OCB on Job Satisfaction. One of the factors forming job satisfaction is Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Satisfied employees are more likely to speak positively about the organization, help coworkers, and make their job performance exceed normal expectations, moreover, satisfied employees may be more likely to comply with the call of duty, because they want to repeat their positive experiences. Wibowo (2019) in his opinion entitled "Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), the Character of Loyalty to the Organization", explains that in the psychological concept, OCB is a psychological attribute that is continuum in nature. This means that OCB moves from the lowest to the highest spectrum.

H10: job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

RESEARCH METHODS

Research plan

This research is designed to provide an explanation of the cause and effect relationship between variables through hypothesis testing, thus the research approach is a descriptive method in the form of an explanation using a quantitative approach. This type of research is exploratory research, which is a type of research that seeks to find new ideas or relationships. Meanwhile, descriptive research is research that aims to describe the nature or characteristics of a particular phenomenon.

Population and sample

The population in this study were 97 frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area. The sampling method is using a saturated sample method or non-probability sample where the entire population is sampled.

Data source

The data sources in this research use primary data and secondary data. According to Silalahi (2012: 289), data sources are divided into two sources, namely primary data taken directly from respondents, including teacher and employee identity data as well as questionnaires. Secondary data is data obtained from other sources that are related to this research. Secondary data sources can be articles, the internet, journals and so on.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Outer Model Analysis

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is an indicator that is assessed based on the correlation between the item score/component score and the construct score, which can be seen from the standardized loading factor which describes the magnitude of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and the construct. An individual reflexive measure is said to be high if it correlates > 0.7 with the construct to be measured, while an outer loading value between 0.5 - 0.6 is considered sufficient.

2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is a measurement model with reflexive indicators assessed based on cross loading of measurements with constructs. If the correlation of a construct with a measurement item is greater than the size of another construct, it shows that their block size is better than that of other blocks. Meanwhile, another method for assessing discriminant validity is by comparing the squareroot of average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Composite reliability is an indicator for measuring a construct that can be seen in the latent variable coefficients view. To evaluate composite reliability, there are two measuring tools, namely internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha. In this measurement, if the value achieved is > 0.70, it can be said that the construct has high reliability.

3. Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's alpha is a reliability test carried out to strengthen the results of composite reliability. A variable can be declared reliable if it has a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7.

4. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test was carried out to determine the relationship between indicators. To find out whether the formative indicators experience multicollinearity by knowing the value of the variance inflation factors (VIF). A variance inflation factors (VIF) value between 5-10 can be said to mean that this indicator has multicollinearity

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity has meaning, namely a set of indicators representing a latent variable and underlying that latent variable. To test convergent validity, the outer loading or loading factor value is used. An indicator is declared to meet convergent validity in the good category if the outer loading value is > 0.7. According to Chin, as quoted by (Ghozali, 2021), an outer loading value between 0.5 - 0.6 is considered sufficient to meet the convergent validity requirements.

2. Discriminant Validity

Table 1. Discriminant validity

Variable	Cross Loading Value	Table	Information
Perception of Organizational Support (X1)	0.691	0.198	Valid
Workload (X2)	0.460	0.198	Valid
Organizational Culture (X3)	0.507	0.198	Valid
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.525	0.198	Valid
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)(Y)	0.627	0.198	Valid

Based on the data presented in table 4.10 above, it can be seen that each indicator in the research variable has a cross loading value > Rtable. Based on the results obtained, it can be stated that the variables used in this research have good discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

3. Composite Reliability

Table 2 Composite Reliability

Variable	CR	Results
Perception of Organizational Support (X1)	0.784	Reliable
Workload (X2)	0.810	Reliable
Organizational Culture (X3)	0.832	Reliable
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.886	Reliable
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)(Y)	0.756	Reliable

Based on the data display in table 4.11 above, it can be seen that the composite reliability value for all research variables is > 0.7. These results indicate that each variable has met composite reliability so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

4. Cronbach Alpha

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha

Variable	C.A	Results
Perception of Organizational Support (X1)	0.697	Reliable
Workload (X2)	0.631	Reliable
Organizational Culture (X3)	0.762	Reliable
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.835	Reliable
OrganizationalCitizenship Behavior (OCB)(Y)	0.631	Reliable

Based on the data display above in table 4.12, it can be seen that the Cronbach alpha value for each research variable is > 0.6-0.7, meaning the value is reliable. Thus, these results can show that each study has met the requirements for the Cronbach alpha value, so it can be concluded that each variable has a high level of reliability.

5. Multicollinearity

Table 5. Multicollinearity

Variable	VIF
Perception of Organizational Support (X1)	1,715
Workload (X2)	2,483
Organizational Culture (X3)	1,875
Job Satisfaction (Z)	4,018

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test, it shows that the VIF (Variance Inflation Factors) value is below 5, so it can be said that multicollinearity does not occur for each of the research variables.

HYPOTHESIS TEST

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics values and P-Values values. The research hypothesis can be declared accepted if the P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of hypothesis testing obtained in this research through the inner model:

The results of testing the direct influence of the relationship between variables using SmartPLS 3.0 can be seen in the following table:

Based on the results of the Sobel test calculation, it shows that the z value (X1) is 9.87, the z value (X2) is 28.2 and the z value (X3) is 18.5 > 1.96 (absolute z value) so that proves that the variable job satisfaction (Z) is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of perceptions of organizational support (X1), workload (X2) and Organizational Culture (X3) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Y).

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on OCB

The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the perception of organizational support, the OCB decreases. This means that even though there is a positive relationship between variables, this relationship is not statistically significant. Even though frontliners do not receive organizational support from the company, they have a spontaneous sense of empathy that comes from implementing organizational culture in the company on a daily basis. There they are required to adopt a lifestyle that is related to the organizational culture of the company. Therefore, employees already have an OCB attitude so they have no influence even if the company does not support it. From the implementation carried out by employees, they are not aware that they have OCB in the form of organizational culture rules in the company.

The Effect of Workload on OCB

The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the workload, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) increases. Even though the workload increases, it does not affect employee OCB, so the higher the employee's workload, the more OCB will increase. Every frontliner employee who gets an additional workload, initially service plus sales, does not make their OCB attitude decrease. Because the higher the workload, the OCB of frontliner employees increases.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on OCB

The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the workload, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) increases. There is an influence between organizational culture and OCB because organizational culture and OCB are very closely linked, where the organizational culture in the company is very high, such as maintaining the principles of AKHLAK in the company, namely trustworthy, competent, harmonious, loyal, adaptive and collaborative. By continuing to apply the AKHLAK principles, each employee's OCB behavior will increase.

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction

The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the perception of organizational support, the greater job satisfaction, which means that even though there is a positive relationship between variables, this relationship is not statistically significant. Every job satisfaction has an indicator and every employee does their work according to the target, so the perception of organizational support is only as complementary support but has no effect on job satisfaction because every employee will feel satisfied with their work if their tasks and work are completed according to the target.

The Effect of Workload on Job Satisfaction

There is an influence between workload and job satisfaction. If each employee has a high workload that is required to meet the target to be achieved. When employees have achieved the target of this high workload, job satisfaction will arise. Likewise, the higher the workload that has not been completed according to the target, the lower their job satisfaction will be. To achieve job satisfaction, employees try to complete these targets so that they get good results and will get even better job satisfaction.

Organizational Culture on Satisfaction

The organizational culture that has been implemented by individuals or teams of employees, namely the AKHLAK principles, which are trustworthy, competent, harmonious, loyal, adaptive and collaborative, has an influence on daily lifestyles, especially within the company. The better they implement organizational culture in the company, the better performance they will get and good work results will create better job satisfaction. If employees do not implement the organizational culture in the company, they will face many obstacles to their work and will result in job satisfaction not being achieved and causing stress levels and not resulting in good performance and targets not being achieved.

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on OCB Through Job Satisfaction

It is important for company employees to get organizational support, the better organizational support the employees get, the more they will automatically provide good OCB behavior. When employees apply OCB to themselves and other people or the surrounding environment, company employees will create a good atmosphere at work. When a good atmosphere is created, it will also produce good performance, so that targets are achieved which will increase employee job satisfaction. As a frontliner, organizational support is important because frontliner employees are the front line in the company, so if organizational support is high, feelings of empathy and OCB behavior will also increase, resulting in satisfaction from both customers and fellow employees.

The Effect of Workload on OCB Through Job Satisfaction

There is a significant influence between workload and employee job satisfaction. The higher the workload received by employees, the more likely they are to experience fatigue so that the OCB's behavior towards themselves, other people and the surrounding environment does not result in job satisfaction. The results of this research are that the higher the employee's workload, the higher the OCB behavior will result in job satisfaction. If employees have completed their targets and work and have job satisfaction, they will continue to implement OCB behavior as they should.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on OCB Through Job Satisfaction

There is a positive and significant influence between organizational culture and employee job satisfaction. The organizational culture in the company that has been implemented by its employees, such as the AKHLAK principles, namely trustworthiness, competence, harmony, loyalty and collaboration, will influence employee OCB behavior. When employees feel satisfied with their work, they will implement the organizational culture well so that they behave OCB towards themselves, their team, customers and their organization.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on OCB

There is an influence between job satisfaction and OCB. Employees who complete work according to targets will create employee job satisfaction, so that employees create a good work atmosphere and produce job satisfaction and increase employee OCB behavior.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that the researcher has explained, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The results show that perceptions of organizational support have no significant effect on OCB in the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
2. The results show that workload has a significant effect on OCB in the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
3. The results show that organizational culture has a significant effect on OCB in the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area
4. The results show that the perception of organizational support does not significantly influence job satisfaction at the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
5. The results show that workload has a significant effect on job satisfaction at the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
6. The results show that the perception of organizational support has a significant effect on OCB through job satisfaction at the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
7. The results show that workload has a significant effect on OCB through job satisfaction at the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
8. The results show that organizational culture has a significant effect on OCB through job satisfaction at the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.
9. The results show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on OCB in the frontliners of PT Bank Mandiri Persero (Tbk) Jember City Area.

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